

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AT M/S SINDOL BAJAJ BIDAR

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ABSTRACT

This temporary role record is an after-effect of the exploration that is carried solely from the ace of business enterprise. During the four semesters of the direction every understudy ought to almost truly educate as a learner inside the association to get halfway information and present a comparable report to acquire these necessities concentrating the “M/s SINDOL BAJAJ BIDAR” capacity of the association as a large component for any affiliation to accomplish goals and makes a speciality of this calls regarding planning at all levels to guarantee the clear working of this document is to understand typically the BAJAJ AUTOMOBILES painting inside connection to diverse partitions. Bajaj Auto Ltd. Is probably the assembling and 3 Wheeler maker in India. The business is super for building R and D, thing advancement, minimal attempt organising and fabricating strategies. The business enterprise is the couple of biggest and 3 wheeled prices inside the state with prices representing 18% of just about all out offers. The corporation has two auxiliaries generally Bajaj Auto International Loge BV and PT Bajaj Indonesia. The organization come to be mounted on April 35, 2007 as it’s entirely possessed backup Bajaj Automobile Ltd. (retaining employer) beneath the call of Bajaj Investment and Holding Limited. The employer were offered its underlining enterprise testimony on, may 7, 2007. Typically the parent employer works inside portion, for instance, automobile, protection and speculation, in addition to that is only typically the tip of the Banquets’. Perceiving development openings inside the vitality, wind, vitality, and account areas, the discern business enterprise erases those physical activities into 3 separate elements, each concentrating on middle enterprise and attractive talents.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction, a term frequently used in marketing, is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation.

Customer satisfaction is defined as “the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals.”

It is seen as a key performance indicator within business and is often part of a balanced scorecard. In a competitive marketplace where businesses compete for customers, customer satisfaction is seen as a key differentiator and increasingly has become a key element of business strategy.

“Within organizations, customer’s satisfaction ratings can have powerful effects. They focus employees on the importance of fulfilling customer’s expectations. Furthermore, when these ratings dip, they warn of problems that can affect sales and profitability. These metrics quantify an important dynamic. When a brand has loyal customers, it gains positive word-of-mouth marketing, which is both free and highly effective.”

Therefore, it is essential for businesses to effectively manage customer satisfaction. To be able do this, firms need reliable and representative measures of satisfaction.

“In researching satisfaction, firms generally ask customers whether their product or service has met or exceeded expectations. Thus, expectations are a key factor behind satisfaction. When customers have high expectation and the reality falls short, they will be disappointed and will likely rate their experience as less than satisfying.”

The internship project is taken place at M/s SINDOL BAJAJ.

The internship project is about CUSTOMER SATISFACTION at M/s SINDOL BAJAJ

1.2 INDUSTRY PROFILE

India is the second largest producer and manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world. It stands next only to Japan and China in terms of the number of two-wheelers produced and domestic sales respectively. Indian two-wheeler industry has got spectacular growth in the last few years. Indian two-wheeler industry had a small beginning in the early 50’s. The Automobile products of India (API) started manufacturing scooters in the country.

Bikes are a major segment of Indian two-wheeler industry, the other two being scooters and mopeds. Indian companies are among the largest two-wheeler manufactures in the world.

In the initial stages, the scooter segment was dominated by API; it was later overtaken by Bajaj Auto. Although various government and private enterprises entered the fray for

scooters, the only new player that has lasted till today is LML. The motorcycle segment was initially dominated by Enfield 350cc bikes and Escorts 175cc bike.

The two-wheeler market was opened to foreign competition in the mid-80s. And the then market leaders – Escorts and Enfield – were caught unaware by the onslaught of the 100cc bikes of the four Indo-Japanese joint ventures. With the availability of fuel efficient low power bikes, demand swelled, resulting in Hero Honda – then the only producer of four stroke bikes (100cc category), gaining a top slot. The first Japanese motorcycles were introduced in the early eighties. TVS Suzuki and Hero Honda brought in the first two-stroke engine motorcycles respectively. These two players initially started with assembly of CKD kits, and later on progressed to indigenous manufacturing. In the 90s the major growth for motorcycle segment was brought in by Japanese motorcycles, which grew at a rate of nearly 25% CAGR in the last five years.

The industry had a smooth ride in the 50s, 60s and 70s when the Government prohibited new entries and strictly controlled capacity expansion. The industry saw a sudden growth in the 80s. The industry witnessed a steady growth of 14% leading to a peak volume of 1.9mn vehicles in 1990. In 1990, the entire automobile industry saw a drastic fall in demand. This resulted in the decline of 15% in 1991 and 8% 1992, resulting production loss of 0.4mn vehicles. Barring Hero Honda, all the major producers suffered from recession in FY93 and FY94. Hero Honda showed a marginal decline in 1992. The reasons for recession in the sector were the incessant rise in fuel prices, high input costs and reduced purchasing power due to significant rise in general price level and credit crunch in consumer financing. Factors like increased production in 1992, due to new entrants coupled with the recession in the industry resulted in company either reporting losses or a fall in profits. key players in the Two-wheeler industry.

There are many two-wheeler manufactures in India. Major players in the 2-wheeler industry are Hero Honda Motors Ltd (HHML), Bajaj Auto Ltd (Bajaj Auto) and TVS Motor Company Ltd (TVS).

The other key players in the two-wheeler industry are Kinetic Motor Company Ltd (KMCL), Kinetic Engineering Ltd (KEL), LML Ltd (LML), and Yamaha Motors India (Yamaha), Majestic Auto Ltd (Majestic Auto), Royal Enfield Ltd (REL) and Honda Motorcycle & Scooter India (P) Ltd (HMSI).

Evolution of two wheeler in India :-

Two-wheeler segment is one of the most important components of the automobile sector that has undergone significant change due to shift in policy environment. The two-wheeler industry has been in existence in the country since 1955. It consists of three segments viz. scooters, motorcycles and mopeds. According to the figures published by SIAM, the share of two-wheelers in automobile sector in terms of units sold was about 80 per cent during 2003-04. This high figure itself is suggestive of the importance of the sector. In the initial years, entry of firms, capacity expansion, choice of products including capacity mix and technology, all critical areas of functioning of an industry, were effectively controlled by the State machinery. The lapses in the system had invited fresh policy options that came into being in late sixties. Amongst these policies, monopolies and Restrictive Trade Practices (MRTP) and Foreign Exchange Regulation Act (FERA) were aimed at regulating monopoly and foreign investment respectively. This controlling mechanism over the industry resulted in:-

(a) Several firms operating below minimum scale of efficiency; (B) Underutilisation of capacity; and (C) usage of outdated technology. Recognition of the damaging effects of licensing and fettering policies led to initiation of reforms, which ultimately took a more prominent shape with the introduction of the New Economic Policy (NEP) in 1985.

However, the major set of reforms was launched in the year 1991 in response to the major macroeconomic crisis faced by the economy. The industrial policies shifted from a regime of regulation and tight control to a more liberalised and competitive era. Two major results of policy changes during these years in two-wheeler industry were that the weaker player died out giving way to the new entrants and superior products and a sizable increase in number of brands entered the market that compelled the firms to compete on the basis of product attributes. Finally, the two-wheeler industry in the country has been able to witness a proliferation of brands with introduction of new technology as well as increase in number of players. However, with various policy measures undertaken in order to increase the competition, though the degree of concentration has been lessened over time, deregulation of the industry has not really resulted in higher level of competition.

There is large untapped market in semi-urban and rural areas of the country. Any strategic planning for the two-wheeler industry needs to identify these markets with the help of available statistical techniques. Potential market can be identified as well as prioritised using these techniques with the help of secondary data on socio-economic parameters. For the two-wheeler industry, it is also important to identify the target groups for various categories of motorcycles and scooters. With the formal introduction of second hand car market by the reputed car manufacturers and easy loan availability for new as well as used cars, the two-wheeler industry needs to upgrade its market information system to capture the new market

and to maintain its already existing markets. Availability of easy credit for two-wheeler in rural and smaller urban areas also requires more focussed attention. It is also imperative to initiate measures to make the presence of Indian two-wheelers industry felt in the global market. Adequate incentives for promoting exports and setting up of institutional mechanism such as Automobile Export Promotion Council would be of great help for further surge in demand for the Indian two-wheeler industry.

National council of Applied Economic Research (NCAER) has forecast two-wheeler demand during the period 2002-03 through 2011-12. The forecast had been made using econometric technique along with inputs obtained from a primary survey conducted at 14 prime cities in the country. Estimations were based on Panel Regression, which takes into account both time series and section variation in data. A panel data of 16 major states over period of 5 years ending 1999 was used for the estimation of parameters. The models considered a large number of macro-economics, demographic and socio-economic variables to arrive at the best estimations for different two-wheeler segment. The projections have been made at all India and regional levels. Different scenarios have been presented based on different assumption regarding the demand drivers of the two-wheeler industry. The most likely scenario assumed annual growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to be 5.5 percent during 2002-03 and was anticipated to increase gradually to 6.5 percent during 2011-12.

1.3 COMPANY PROFILE

Bajaj Auto Ltd. (BAL) any of the two and three assembling producers in India. The employer is known for its L and D item development and assembling capabilities. The particular agency is the biggest exporter of and 3 wheels inside the empire. The employer has two backups to be particular Bajaj Auto International Cooperation BV and PT Bajaj Indonesia.

On November twenty nine, 1945 Bajaj Auto arrived for the sake of M/s Bacha raj Investing Corporation Private Limited. Within 1948 Bajaj Auto started out to promote and 3 wheels imported in India. In the 50s Bajaj Auto gained allow from the Government of India to make two wheels. In 1960 Bajaj Auto became an open up corporation.

In 1971 Bajaj Auto propelled a three-wheeler administrator. In 1977 the organization propelled a Back Engine Auto Rickshaw. Within nineteenth 1984, the organization stone

became made for the brand new Bajaj Auto processing plant at WALUJ Aurangabad. November 5, 1985 Bajaj Auto began technology on the WALUJ plant. In 1988 Bajaj Auto started generation at the Chakan Pune Grow. In November 2001, Bajaj Auto propelled the beautiful bicycle 'Pulsar'.

In Feb 2003 Bajaj Auto powered the a hundred and fifteen Calibres within the traditional engine fragment. Because based on the Arrangement of Demerger scheme Bajaj Holdings and Investment Ltd. (BAL BHAL erode) is assessed into 3 assignments with impact form a hit day of Viz. February 20, 2008. The protecting company works in fragments, for instance, safety and different car and project.

Perceiving the improvement openings inside the safety and budgetary a part of power sparing breeze vitality organization made those physical games be three separate factors that each can deal with middle enterprise and engage fitness. Consequently claims the figure enterprise with all blessings and liabilities included into the hobby in PT Bajaj Auto Indonesia and in a few merchant businesses are moved to Bajaj Investment and Holding Ltd (BHIL). Moreover, a sum of Rs.15000 million in real cash and money reciprocals are likewise moved to Investment and Holding Ltd. As major elements of the Bajaj Holdings and Investment Ltd plan changed to Bajaj Auto Ltd (BAL). The rule date might be close on March 31, 2007.

On April nine, 2007, the organization got a take care of the inexperienced plant processing plant in Uttarakhand. In the primary 12 months of plant activity it created 275000 motors. The gathering plant business enterprise in Akurdi closes on account that September 3, 2007 because of better era prices. In November 2007, Bajaj Auto International Holdings BV gained a 14. Fifty one % stake in KTM Power Sports activities automobile manufacturer in Europe for Rs.345 Crore.

During 2007-08 the business propelled the XCD one hundred twenty five DTS-Si and the entice of the Direct Injected auto tricycle. Chakan commercial facility finishes aggregate introduction of more than 2 million Pulsar. In 2009-10, the corporate extended its introduction restriction of Motorized Two and three Wheelers via 300000 Nos to 4260000 Nos. The enterprise began Pulsar 220F pulsar a hundred and eighty UG Pulsar one hundred thirty five LS and looked via DTS- Si available. In 2010-11 the business enterprise created two and three Wheelers engine generation restrict by way of 780000 Nos to 5040000 Nos. The organization offers the Avenger 220 DTS-I KTM DUKE a hundred twenty five found 150 and one hundred twenty five in the market. The enterprise intends to maintain up and 3 wheelers restriction at the existing diploma of 5040000 number every year before the finish of

March 31, 2012. The significance of 4 wheel car development in progress and the primary business dispatch of the platform is booked for in 2012 Bajaj Auto is tied with Kawasaki Japan at Indonesia.

2.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Customer satisfaction occurs when the data obtain from business match belief. Customer may not remember experience the game expectation even though, customer will frequently notice and keep in mind those that deviated from intimation. This stage is mainly known as disappointment results in to a feeling of clash in cash where an experience obtains from product logic falls short of expectation.

In literature antecedents of satisfaction are studied from different aspects. The considerations extend from psychological to physical and from normative to positive aspects. However, in most of the cases the consideration is focused on two basic constructs as customer's expectations prior to purchase or use of a product and his relative perception of the performance of that product after using it.

A customer's expectations about a product tell us how he or she anticipated how that product will perform. As it is suggested in the literature, consumers may have various "Types" of expectation when forming opinions about a product's anticipated performance. **Ex:** Four types of expectations are identified by **Miller, (1977)**: Ideal, expected, minimum tolerable, and desirable. **While, Day (1977)**: Indicated among expectations, the ones that are about the costs, the product nature, and the efforts in obtaining benefits and lastly expectations of social values. Perceived product performance is considered as an important construct due to its ability to allow making comparisons with the expectations.

It is considered that customer judge product on a limited set of norms and attributes. **Olshavsky and miller (1972) and Olson and Dover (1976)** designed their researches as to manipulate actual product performance, and their aim was to find out how perceived performance ratings were influenced by expectations.

"These Studies took out the discussions about explaining the differences between expectations and perceived performance."

In some research studies, scholars have been able to establish that customer satisfaction has a strong emotional, i.e, affective, component. Still others show that the cognitive and affective components of customer satisfaction reciprocally influence each other over time to determine overall satisfaction.

Especially for durable goods that are consumed over time, there is value to taking a dynamic perspective on customer satisfaction. Within a dynamic perspective, customer satisfaction can evolve over time as customers repeatedly use a product or interact with a service. The satisfaction experienced with each interaction (transactional satisfaction) can influence the overall, cumulative satisfaction. Scholars showed that it is not just overall customer satisfaction, but also customer loyalty that evolves over time.

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW WITH RESEARCH GAP

Vavra, T.G. (1997): Satisfaction has been generally defined as “A satisfaction post-purchase involvement with a product or services given existing buying expectations.

Terry Grapentine (2019): Satisfaction is an ambiguous concept; the marketing literature does not offer a uniform definition of the satisfaction concept; satisfaction can be emotion, satisfaction can be cognition; and how to approach the satisfaction concept in applied research.

Zoe Dowling (2020): Customer experience matters. People are inundated with choices for every product and services that they use and they are making decisions differently than in years gone by. Today, customer experience (CX) is a deciding factor. Expectations are high and CX effectiveness easily makes or breaks the purchase decision.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To know customer satisfaction towards Bajaj Two Wheeler Bikes.

Consequently the administration has wanted to lead “A project report on customer satisfaction towards Bajaj Two Wheeler Bike, Bidar.

3.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY

This research is done to know the Mind-Set of the customer, with the help of which the organization will become alert of their pitfalls or Drawbacks and in turn also make

improvements in the product about the level of satisfaction of the customer towards their offerings in the marketplace.

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the customer satisfaction level toward features and services offered by Bajaj Auto .Ltd.
- To know about services which are provided by the company.
- To gain inputs form customers to improve satisfaction.
- To study and understand the areas which are need to be improved.
- To know company objectives about feature modification in Bajaj motor.
- To know opinion about price of Bajaj Motor Cycle.
- To Discover an elements impact client to obtain Bajaj motors.
- To find out customers are more like to occasional Discount/Free gift offered by Bajaj Motor.

3.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study helps in findings out the level of customer satisfaction of Bajaj Auto Ltd. Customers. The scope is confirmed only to examine the “Customer satisfaction” with reference to Bajaj Bikes” and to find possible remedies to contract and neutralize their competition. The Study helps to know the feedback and suggestions from the customers.

It also explained the benefits required by the company as a result of services, it has also studies the level of customer has regarding the service provided by them. It also focusing is to provide more awareness to return people about their service and also helps to maintain goodwill in the market.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is an original contribution to the existing stock of knowledge making for its advancement. It is the pursuit of truth with the help of study, observation, comparison and experiment. In short the search for knowledge through objectives and systematic method of findings solution to a problem in research.

A research method refers to the methods the researchers use in performing research operations. Research Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. By research methodology not only the research methods are considered but also the logic behind the methods used in the context of the research study and explanations are given on why a particular technique is used.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

The research design that is adopted in this study is Descriptive Research.

DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH:

To describe the characteristics of the variables in situation.

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION:

Sources of Data:

Data were collected through both primary and secondary data sources.

❖ Primary Data:

A primary data is a data, which is collected afresh and for the first time, and thus Happen to be original in character. The primary data with the help of questionnaire were collected from various investors.

❖ Secondary Data:

Secondary Data consist of information that already exists somewhere, have been collected. Secondary Data is collected from Company websites, other websites, Magazines, Books

SAMPLING DESIGN

Sampling Method:

The sampling technique used is Simple Random Sampling.

Sample Size:

The Sample size for this study is 150 customers of Bajaj Auto.ltd in Bidar city.

3.6 HYPOTHESES

H₀- There is relationship exist between two questions.

H₁- There is No relationship exists between two questions.

H₀ – There is a significant positive relationship between the Bajaj motors company and the customers.

H₁ - It is clear that customer's satisfaction in today's dynamic corporate environment is very essential. On the other hand dissatisfaction has been seen as a primary reason for customer's intentions to switch. Dissatisfied customers are more likely to tell almost ten people their unfortunate experiences with a particular organization.

Customer satisfaction highly influences customer's repurchase intension. Satisfied customers are most likely to share their experiences with other four or six people around them. This organization must be able to build and maintain long lasting relationship with customers through satisfying various customer needs and demands which eventually motivates them to continue to do business with the organization on-going basis.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 HOW DO YOU COME TO KNOW ABOUT BAJAJ BIKES?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Advertisement	14	28
Friends / Relatives	26	52
Social media	6	12
Internet	0	0
Magazine	0	0
Others	4	8
Total	50	100

INTERPRATION:

From the above graph it is showing that 28% customers are know the name of Bajaj through Advertisement, 52% from Friends / Relatives, 12% from Social media, 0% from Internet, 0% from Magazine, and 8% from Others.

4.2 HAVE YOU VISITED SINDOL BAJAJ SHOWROOM?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Yes	44	88
No	6	12
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph is showing that 88% of people visited the Sindol Bajaj Showroom and 12% people not visited.

4.3 WHICH BIKE DO YOU LIKE IN THE BAJAJ?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Pulsar	33	66
CT100	8	16
Platina	4	8
Discover	5	10
Other	0	0
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph it is showing that 66% Customers like the Pulsar Bike in Bajaj, 16% CT 100, 8% Platina, 10% Discover and 0% other Bikes.

4.4 RATE THE FACTORES EFFECTING THE PURCHASE DECISION?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Price	16	32
Brand image	16	32
Mileage	10	20
Power	7	14
Style	1	2
Other	0	0
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph it is showing that which factor affecting the customers to make a purchase decision in that 32% price effects the customers, 32% Brand Image, 20% mileage, 14% Power and the 2% style.

4.5 WHAT IS YOUR OPINION ABOUT PRICE OF BAJAJ MOTOR CYCLE?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Affordable	34	68
Competitive	10	20
Comparatively high	6	12
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph is showing that the opinion about Price of Bajaj Motor Cycle According to the customers 68% Affordable, 20% Competitive and 12% comparatively high.

4.6 HOW DO YOU FEEL ABOUT ADVERTISING STRATEGY OF BAJAJ?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Motivate	26	52
Informative	18	36
Makes no difference	6	12
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph it is showing that the opinion about Advertising strategy of Bajaj motor cycles through customers 52% Motivate, 36% Informative and 12% Makes no difference.

4.7 WHAT FEATURE DO YOU LIKE TO DEVELOP IN BAJAJ MOTOR CYCLE TO MAKE IT AS THE BEST?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Engine	8	16
Suspension	5	10
Tyre	11	22
Mileage	9	18
Discs	11	22
Seats	6	12
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph it is showing that the 16% customers like to develop Engine, 10% Suspension, 22% Tyre, 18% mileage, 22% Discs and the 12% Seats in the Bajaj motor cycle to make it as the best.

4.8 ARE THE SPARE PARTS AVAILABLE AT THE SERVICE CENTRE, WHERE YOU DEAL WITH?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Yes	45	90
No	5	10
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph is showing that the 90% customers say that Spare parts available at the service centre and 10% customers say not available.

4.9 IF THE COMPANY OFFERS ANY EXCHANGE MELA, WILL YOU GO FOR A NEW ONE?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Yes	14	28
No	36	72
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph is showing that if the company offers any exchange mela, 28% of Customers interested to go for new one but 72% customers not interested go for new one.

4.10 DID YOU LIKE OUR SERVICES? IF YES, WHAT WAS THE EXPERIENCE?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Excellent	13	26
Good	28	56
Average	9	18
Poor	0	0
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph showing that the 26% is Excellent, 56% is Good, 18% is Average and 0% is poor Service of Bajaj in according to customers' experience.

4.11 DO YOU RECOMMEND YOUR FRIENDS / RELATIVES TO PURCHASE THE BAJAJ BIKES?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Yes	47	94
No	3	6
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph showing that 94% of Customers recommend their friends / relatives to purchase the Bajaj bikes and 6% of customers not recommend.

4.12 DURATION OF USING THE BAJAJ MOTOR CYCLE?

Scale	No. of respondent	Percentage
Below 1 year	19	38
1-3 year	21	42
3-6 year	7	14
Above 6 years	3	6
Total	50	100

INTERPRATATION:

From the above graph it is showing that Duration of customers using the Bajaj Motor Cycle in that 38% of customers using below 1 year, 42% from 1-3 years , 14% from 3-6 years and 6% above 6 years.

5. FINDINGS

- I found that 28% customers are know the name of Bajaj through Advertisement, 52% from Friends / Relatives, 12% from Social media, 0% from Internet, 0% from Magazine, and 8% from Others.
- I found that 66% Customers like the Pulsar Bike in Bajaj, 16% CT 100, 8% Platina, 10% Discover and 0% other Bikes.
- I found that which factor affecting the customers to make a purchase decision in that 32% price effects the customers, 32% Brand Image, 20% mileage, 14% Power and the 2% style.
- I found that the opinion about Price of Bajaj Motor Cycle According to the customers 68% Affordable, 20% Competitive and 12% comparatively high
- I found that the opinion about Advertising strategy of Bajaj motor cycles through customers 52% Motivate, 36% Informative and 12% Makes no difference.
- I found that the 16% customers like to develop Engine, 10% Suspension, 22% Tyre, 18% mileage, 22% Discs and the 12% Seats in the Bajaj motor cycle to make it as the best.
- I found that the 26% is Excellent, 56% is Good, 18% is Average and 0% is poor Service of Bajaj in according to customers' experience.
- I found that satisfactory of customer's problems solved by the company 26% of customers Highly satisfied, 64% of satisfied, 6% of somewhat satisfied and 4% of customers Dissatisfied.
- I found that Duration of customers using the Bajaj Motor Cycle in that 38% of customers using below 1 year, 42% from 1-3 years , 14% from 3-6 years and 6% above 6 years
- I found that 86% of customers receiving Bajaj Service reminders regularly and 14% of customers not receiving regularly.

6.CONCLUSION

To conclude the final project on “CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ON M/S SINDOL BAJAJ BIDAR”. I have received both favourable and unfavourable responses from the respondents. I have met 50 customers of different places and accommodated at M/S SINDOL BAJAJ BIDAR and findings were enlightened to me. The project work has helped in studying and understanding the practicalities of organization. The study of “CUSTOMER SATISFACTION” towards on M/S BAJAJ SINDOL BIDAR the data was collected from various sources and also through the tools like Questionnaire and relevant interaction with concerned persons. By seeing the performance of Bajaj Two Wheeler vehicle service provide by the Bajaj motors can conclude that it has wide marketplace and incredible hope for it sales.

Also in the current market it is one of the leading vehicles. The supply and availability of the vehicle in Bidar locality is very best. As per show room was troubled is have excellent prospects in close to aspect it is given that good service majority of the people are satisfied with Bajaj company vehicle.

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